

SMART PHONE ADDICTION AND INTERNET ADDICTION; IT'S ASSOCIATED RISK FACTOR: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY OF MALE BOARDER STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF MALAKAND

Atta Ullah¹, Habib Ullah Khan², Fawad Ullah³, Sayyed Naeem⁴, Wajahat Ullah⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Department of Statistics University of Malakand, Chakdara, Dir Lower, KPK, Pakistan

¹attaullaharsalan34@gmail.com, ²habibullah858@uom.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15877240>

Keywords

Smartphone Addiction, Internet Addiction, Risk Factors, University Students

Article History

Received: 10 April, 2025

Accepted: 15 June, 2025

Published: 12 July, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Habib Ullah Khan

Abstract

The undergraduate stage is crucial in a student's academic journey. Smartphone use can lead to smartphone addiction, which is a growing concern worldwide. With greater digital access, behavioral addictions, particularly excessive smartphone and internet use, have become prevalent among university students, affecting their academic performance, mental health, and social interactions. This study examines smartphone and internet addiction among male hostel students at the University of Malakand, using data from 400 students collected via the Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS) and the Internet Addiction Test (IAT). Results indicated a significant portion of students experienced moderate to high addiction levels, with 55% reporting adverse academic effects and over 50% suffering from sleep disturbances due to late-night usage. A strong correlation was found between smartphone and internet addiction ($r = 0.606$), with phone addiction predicting internet addiction ($p < 0.001$). Age was a small but significant factor, showing older students had lower addiction levels. Other factors, like semester and degree program, were not significant. The study emphasizes the need for digital awareness programs and mental health support in university hostels, suggesting early interventions to help students manage technology use. Future research should include female participants and consider long-term effects.

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, mobile phones and the internet have become integral to daily life, especially for adolescents and young adults. While these technologies offer unprecedented access to communication, information, and entertainment, their excessive and uncontrolled use has given rise to significant behavioral and psychological challenges. Mobile Phone Addiction (MPA) and Internet Addiction (IA) have emerged as pressing public health concerns worldwide, particularly among university students, a group uniquely vulnerable due

to academic stress, transitional life stages, and constant exposure to digital media.

A study in China found that 36.6% of undergraduate students experience mobile phone addiction, leading to significant psychological issues and health problems. The risk is particularly high among those using their phones for over four hours daily Mei et al, (2023)

A study conducted on 545 undergraduate students at Umm Al-Qura University revealed a high prevalence of smartphone addiction (67%) among participants, primarily females under 21. The research highlighted

significant negative impacts, such as lower academic performance, physical inactivity, and mental health issues, emphasizing the need for smartphone education to address these concerns Alotaibi et al. (2022)

Mobile phone addiction (MPA) and internet addiction (IA) are interconnected, with a study showing a positive correlation between the two among undergraduates, particularly with female students exhibiting higher levels of MPA. This raises concerns about shared risk factors and the consequences of dual addictions (2013).

Beyond general health consequences, digital addiction negatively influences key psychosocial attributes. A study conducted in Egypt on 180 nursing students revealed a strong inverse relationship between IA and emotional intelligence ($r = -0.53$, $p < 0.001$), including components like emotional perception, self-regulation, and empathy. Internet addiction was a significant negative predictor of emotional intelligence, accounting for 30.5% of its variance El Gazer et al (2024). Given that emotional intelligence is critical for interpersonal relationships and professional performance—especially in health-related fields—these findings highlight the far-reaching impact of digital addiction.

A study conducted at Umm Al-Qura University in Saudi Arabia found that 67% of undergraduate students are addicted to smartphones, significantly impacting their academic performance, physical health, and mental well-being. The most affected students were typically aged ≤ 21 , unemployed, and from higher-income families. The findings underscore the need for educational initiatives on the health consequences of smartphone addiction among university students Alotaibi et al. (2022).

Cultural and regional studies also reflect the growing scope of the problem. In Iran, IA and MPA were found to be significantly associated with loneliness in adolescents, while another study noted a high prevalence of these addictions among Iranian students, calling for urgent preventive measures Mirhadian et al. and Hasandost et al. (2018, 2016). Similarly, in South Korea, a study of 768 junior high students categorized individuals into addiction groups—non-addicted, smartphone addicted, internet addicted, and dual addicted. Results showed that

addiction risk was influenced by psychological, family, and school environments, with different profiles associated with smartphone and internet use Jeong et al. (2020).

Moreover, Whitaker et al. (2020) proposed a nuanced distinction between physiological and psychological bases of MPA. Using data from 1,219 university students in the US and South Korea, they found that some individuals' addiction was related to excessive time use without severe psychological symptoms, while others displayed strong psychological vulnerabilities such as impulsiveness, anxiety, and hopelessness, even without prolonged usage. This dual pathway model suggests that MPA may not be a uniform condition and requires personalized approaches to intervention and treatment.

While technological advancement has brought immense benefits, these findings demonstrate that mobile phone and internet addiction can adversely affect emotional stability, mental health, academic performance, and quality of life. Moreover, the interaction between MPA and IA, as well as the mediating role of factors like gender, age, psychological distress, and emotional intelligence, remains insufficiently understood. Addressing these gaps is crucial for devising informed strategies to mitigate the rising tide of digital dependency.

A study on smartphone addiction among 545 undergraduate students at Umm Al-Qura University revealed that 67% were addicted, with significant associations to lower academic performance, physical inactivity, and mental health issues. The findings highlight the need for educational initiatives addressing the health impacts of smartphone addiction Alotaibi et al. (2022).

New technologies like the Internet and mobile phones facilitate communication and emotional expression but may also lead to addictive behaviors, particularly among teenagers and young adults. Cultural differences influence vulnerability, with individuals in Asian countries showing higher risks for problematic use, raising concerns about addiction diagnosis and its effects Renau et al. (2015).

Therefore, this research aims to comprehensively examine the prevalence, relationship, and psychological correlates of mobile phone and internet addiction among university students. By

analyzing their influence on emotional intelligence, mental well-being, and sleep quality, the study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of digital addiction and support the development of effective policies and interventions in educational and clinical settings.

Methodology

For the study on smartphone addiction, internet addiction, and their risk factors among male boarder students at the University of Malakand. The study is about smartphone addiction, internet addiction that

recruited male boarder students at the University of Malakand. Among many departments of different faculties, a sample having 400 students is randomly selected from the hostelized students. We have the following type of distribution for the participants. A meticulously designed questionnaire was utilized as the primary instrument for collecting the requisite data. The questionnaire has 14 thoughtful questions on various subjects, which include the Internet usage time, stress level, sleep quality, and academic performance.

Table 1: Likert Scale

0	<i>Not Applicable</i>	3	<i>Frequently</i>
1	<i>Rarely</i>	4	<i>Often</i>
2	<i>Occasionally</i>	5	<i>Always</i>

The researcher visited each Hostel and obtained the necessary permission from the relevant authorities before approaching the students. The researcher guided the participants with a concise overview of the research objectives to the students, ensuring they understood the purpose and context of the research. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed

among all of the undergraduate students from the hostelized students. A total of 340 questionnaires were completed and returned by the participants. Once the respondents submitted their questionnaires, the researcher expressed gratitude for their participation in the study.

Table 2: Data analysis of summarized collected data

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	17	2	0.60%
	18	12	3.50%
	19	42	12.40%
	20	87	25.60%
	21	58	17.10%
	22	65	19.10%
	23	39	11.50%
	24	28	8.20%
	25	7	2.90%
Degree	BS	320	94.10%
	Pharm-D	20	5.90%
Semester	1	95	27.94%

2	1	0.30%	
3	8	2.35%	
4	83	24.40%	
5	2	0.60%	
6	88	25.88%	
7	2	0.6	
8	56	16.47%	
9	1	0.30%	
10	10	2.90%	
Hostel	External	183	53.82%
	Internal	157	46.18%

In this study, the most common age is 20 years (25.6% of students). The majority of students are between 19 and 22 years old. Very few students are older than 24 or younger than 18, meaning the sample is largely traditional university-aged males. The age distribution shows a normal bell-shaped curve, with a slight right skew due to a few older students. A significant majority of the participants (94.1%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science (BS) programs. Only 5.9% of the sample were students pursuing a Doctor of Pharmacy (Pharm-D) degree. This imbalance suggests the research findings are most applicable to BS students, with limited generalizability to other academic backgrounds. The data shows that the majority of the participants were from the 1st (27.94%), 4th (24.4%), and 6th (25.88%) semesters, indicating greater engagement from early to mid-level students. Participation was minimal from students in odd-numbered or higher semesters, such as the 10th semester (2.9%) and others below 1%. This distribution might reflect

either the hostel occupancy patterns at the University of Malakand or varying levels of availability or interest across academic stages. This has implications for interpreting the study's results, as behavior patterns may differ between early and later semesters. The results in and the accompanying bar chart show the distribution of respondents based on their hostel residency type. A total of 183 students (53.82%) were residing in external hostels, while 157 students (46.18%) were living in internal university hostels. The relatively even split between internal and external hostel students allows for a meaningful comparison in assessing smartphone and internet addiction behavior across different living environments.

Inferential data analysis

Here we provide the inferential statistical analysis of the data collected. We used frequency distribution and regression analysis, correlation for inferential analysis.

Table 3: Do you often find that you stay online longer than you intend?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	20	5.9%
Rarely	91	26.8%
Occasionally	82	24.1%
Frequently	44	12.9%
Often	44	12.9%
Always	59	17.4%
Total	340	100%

A survey revealed that 26.8% of students "Rarely" exceed their online time, while 24.1% do so "Occasionally." Notably, 17.4% of students indicated "Always," indicating potential addictive behavior.

Overall, 94.1% experience unplanned extended internet use, highlighting the necessity for awareness programs on healthy internet habits and time management.

Table 4: How often do you neglect household chores to spend more time online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	25	7.4%
Rarely	85	25%
Occasionally	100	29.4%
Frequently	65	19.1%
Often	50	14.7%
Always	25	7.4%
Total	340	100%

A significant number of students (29.4%) occasionally neglect household chores due to internet use, while 25% do so rarely. However, over 41% report moderate to high levels of neglect, indicating potential behavioral issues linked to internet use. Only 7.4% found the question not applicable, suggesting they may not have household responsibilities. These findings highlight the need for awareness campaigns and digital wellness programs in hostel environments. The perception of male Boarder students at the University of Malakand, that

student's How often do you prefer the excitement of the internet to intimacy with your partner via table 4.8. 16.2% of the students marked the question as "Not applicable", suggesting they may not currently be in a relationship. The most common response was "Rarely" (22.9%), followed closely by "Occasionally" (22.4%) and "Frequently" (20.6%). A smaller proportion of students selected "Often" (11.8%) and "Always" (5.9%), which indicates that a minority show a consistent preference for internet use over intimacy.

Table 5: How often do you prefer the excitement of the internet to intimacy with your partner?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	55	16.2%
Rarely	78	22.9%
Occasionally	76	22.4%
Frequently	70	20.6%
Often	40	11.8%
Always	20	5.9%
Total	340	100%

These findings suggest that while most students do not frequently substitute intimacy with internet use, a significant portion still experience moderate to high levels of preference for digital engagement over

physical relationships. This may highlight a growing concern about the potential impact of internet addiction on social and emotional well-being.

Table 6: How often do you form new relationship with fellow online user?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	49	14.4%
Rarely	104	30.6%
Occasionally	58	17.1%
Frequently	63	18.5%
Often	46	13.5%
Always	20	5.9%
Total	340	100%

A majority of students (30.6%) rarely form new online relationships, while 37.9% engage in them frequently or more. Additionally, 17.1% do so occasionally and 13.5% often. Only 5.9%

consistently form online relationships, indicating some reliance on digital interaction. Overall, this moderate level of engagement raises potential concerns about internet addiction and diminished offline social skills.

Table 7: How often do others in your life complain to you about the amount of time you spend online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	54	15.9%
Rarely	85	25.0%
Occasionally	49	14.4%
Frequently	75	22.1%
Often	36	10.6%
Always	41	12.1%
Total	340	100%

A significant portion of students report receiving complaints about their online activity, with 25% stating it's "rarely" and 22.1% experiencing frequent complaints. Worryingly, 12.1% face constant

complaints, highlighting potential issues with internet usage. In total, 44.8% report moderate to high concern from others. This suggests notable effects related to excessive internet or smartphone use among students.

Table 8: How often do your grades or school work suffer because of the amount of time you spend online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	34	10.0%
Rarely	100	29.4%
Occasionally	70	20.6%
Frequently	48	14.1%
Often	50	14.7%
Always	38	11.2%
Total	340	100%

Nearly 55% of male boarder students at the University of Malakand report some academic impact from internet usage, with 40% indicating frequent to always being affected. While about 30% experience minimal disruption, over 60% acknowledge a decline in grades due to excessive

internet use. This highlights the need for awareness campaigns and time management strategies. Support through mental health or counseling may also be necessary to help students balance their internet usage and academic performance.

Table 9: How often do you become defensive or secretive when anyone asks you what you online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	68	20.1%
Rarely	108	31.9%
Occasionally	66	19.5%
Frequently	43	12.7%
Often	35	10.3%
Always	19	5.6%
Total	340	100%

A significant majority of students (71.5%) at the University of Malakand are not overly secretive about their online activities, indicating low to moderate concern. However, 28.5% exhibit frequent secretive behaviors, which may suggest issues like internet

misuse or online dependency. These behaviors could signal early signs of internet addiction. Therefore, implementing awareness programs and mental health interventions is crucial to promote healthier digital habits among students.

Table 10: How often do you block out disturbing thoughts about your life with soothing thoughts of the internet?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	29	8.5%
Rarely	73	21.5%
Occasionally	69	20.3%
Frequently	75	22.1%
Often	46	13.5%
Always	48	14.1%
Total	340	100%

Most students at the University of Malakand reported using the internet to block out disturbing thoughts, with 75 indicating they do so frequently. A significant percentage also noted rare (21.5%) and occasional (20.3%) use, while 14.1% admitted to always relying on this behavior. Only 8.5% felt it was

not applicable to them. These findings suggest a concerning trend of using the internet as an emotional escape, which may lead to internet addiction and mental health issues if not addressed.

Table 11: How often do you snap yell or act annoyed if someone bothers you while you are online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	43	12.6%
Rarely	115	33.8%
Occasionally	89	26.2%
Frequently	36	10.6%
Often	31	9.1%
Always	29	8.5%
Total	340	100%

The majority of boarder male students at the University of Malakand reported feeling annoyed rarely (115 students) or occasionally (89 students) during online disturbances. However, a notable

minority experiences frequent irritation, with 28% admitting to snapping or getting annoyed frequently, often, or always. This could suggest a potential behavioral sign of smartphone or internet addiction, indicating a growing dependency on online activities.

Table 12: How often do you lose sleep due to being online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	32	9.4%
Rarely	63	18.5%
Occasionally	63	18.5%
Frequently	69	20.3%
Often	58	17.1%
Always	55	16.2%
Total	340	100%

The data shows that the majority of male boarder students at the University of Malakand reported their internet use is affecting their sleep patterns. About 53.6% admitted to losing sleep frequently, often, or always, with the highest response being

"Frequently" from 69 students. "Rarely" and "Occasionally" were reported by around 63 each, while "Often" and "Always" were around 58 and 56, respectively. This trend raises concerns about the impact of digital activity on sleep, posing risks to mental and physical health.

Table 13: How often do you find yourself saying "just a few more minutes" when online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	32	9.4%
Rarely	63	18.5%
Occasionally	63	18.5%
Frequently	69	20.3%

Often	58	17.1%
Always	55	16.2%
Total	340	100%

The most common response is that the highest number of students chose "Frequently" about 69 students. Rarely and occasionally were also very close, about 63 each. Often and always were slightly lower, with about 58 and 56 students respectively. Not applicable was selected by around 32 students.

Data clearly shows that procrastination and difficulty disengaging from online activities are common among boarder male students at the University of Malakand. Over half of the respondents struggle with controlling the time spent online, suggesting a significant behavioral sign of internet addiction.

Table 14: How often do you try to cut down the amount of time you spend online and fail?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	25	7.4%
Rarely	70	20.6%
Occasionally	70	20.6%
Frequently	67	19.7%
Often	62	18.2%
Always	48	14.1%

The data indicates that over half of the boarder male students at the University of Malakand struggle to manage their internet usage, reflecting signs of potential internet addiction. The majority responded with Rarely (70) and Occasionally (70), while a significant number also reported Frequently (67) and

Often (62). Although fewer students indicated Always (48), the Not applicable category (25) suggests some may not view excessive online time as a problem. Overall, many students recognize the issue but find it challenging to control their internet habits, time as an issue for them.

Table 15: How often do you try to hid how long you been online?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	30	8.8%
Rarely	75	22.1%
Occasionally	57	16.8%
Frequently	66	19.4%
Often	59	17.4%
Always	51	15.0%
Total	340	100%

The survey results indicate that 75 students reported rarely hiding their online usage, while 66 students responded frequently. Occasionally and often had similar responses, with 57-59 students each. About

51 students claimed to always hide their usage, and 30 chose not applicable, suggesting a significant number of students display signs of problematic internet behavior.

Table 16: How often do you chose to spend more time online over going out with others?

Response Optioned	Frequency	Percentage
Not applicable	30	8.8%
Rarely	75	22.1%
Occasionally	57	16.8%
Frequently	66	19.4%
Often	59	17.4%
Always	51	15.0%
Total	340	100%

The table indicates that the most common response is Rarely (1), selected by approximately 75 students. Frequently (3) follows with about 66 students. Occasionally (2) and Often (4) are similar, with around 57-59 students each. Always (5) has about 51 students, while Not applicable (0) was chosen by

around 30 students. The data suggests a significant number of students spend more time online.

Regression Model and Its Coefficients Table for Internet Addiction

Following table shows the estimated parameters of the regression model.

Table 17: The Estimated Parameters Of The Regression Model

Term	Coef	SE Coef	T-Value	P-Value	VIF
Constant	19.79	7.42	2.67	0.008	
Degree	2.00	2.09	0.95	0.341	1.06
Semester	0.092	0.22	0.42	0.67	1.88
Hostel	-0.343	0.72	-0.48	0.63	1.01
Age	-0.697	0.33	-2.10	0.036	1.93
Score of phone	0.8766	0.06	13.7	0.000	1.01

The constant is the y intercept means when all predictors are zero, the expected score of internet is 19.79. A single unit increase in degree is associated with an increase of 2.00 in internet score, but not statistically significant (P=0.341). Semester have minimal positive effect, not significant. Hostel status have slight negative effect, but not significant. Age have negative effect (-0.697), significant at P=0.036. Older age slightly lowers internet score. Score of

Phone addiction have very strong positive effect (0.8766), highly significant (P=0.000). Higher phone score strongly predicts higher internet score. Also the VIF values around 1-2 indicate no multicollinearity problems.

Regression Equation for Internet Addiction

$$\text{Score of internet} = 19.79 + 2.00 \times \text{degree} + 0.093 \times \text{Semester} - 0.343 \times \text{Hostel} - 0.697 \times \text{Age} + 0.8766 \times \text{Score of phone Addiction}$$

You can plug in values for degree, semester, hostel, Age, and Score of phone to predict the internet score.

The model is pretty good at predicting internet scores (about 38% variance explained). The score of phone (phone usage score) is the strongest predictor of internet score. More phone usage predicts more

internet use. Age has a small but significant negative effect: older students tend to have slightly lower internet scores. Degree program, semester, and hostel living don't have a significant direct effect. Some data points are unusual or outliers, they don't fit the model well and might need special attention.

Metric	Value
R-squared	36.91%
Adjusted R ²	35.96%
Predicted R ²	34.29%
Standard error	5.46

The model explains about **36.91%** of the variance in phone addiction scores. This is a moderate level of explanatory power. The standard error of the estimate is 5.46, indicating the average deviation of the predicted values from the actual values.

Only the internet addiction score is a statistically significant predictor of phone addiction (P < 0.001).

Regression Equation for Phone Addiction

Predicto	Coef	P value	Interpretation
(Consta	16.27	0.001	Intercept of the model
nt)			
Degree	0.23	0.871	✗ Not significant
Semester	0.064	0.675	✗ Not significant
Hostel	0.285	0.566	✗ Not significant
Age	0.065	0.777	✗ Not significant
Score of	0.4134	0.000	✓ Significant predictor
internet			

$$\text{Phone Addiction Score} = 16.27 - 0.23 \times \text{degree} + 0.064 \times \text{semester} - 0.285 \times \text{hostel} + 0.065 \times \text{Age} + 0.4134 \times \text{Internet Score}$$

This is the model you can use to predict the phone addiction score. The regression model is statistically significant overall. The internet addiction score is the only significant predictor of phone addiction.

Age, semester, degree program, and hostel status do not significantly affect phone addiction. The model explains about **37%** of the variation in phone addiction, which is reasonable for behavioral data.

Correlation

Table 20: The Correlation Between Different Variables

Variables	Age	Internet Score	Phone Score	Screen Time	Sleep Hours	Academic Score
Age	–	0.155	0.060	0.012	0.045	0.105
p-value		0.004	0.269	0.545	0.112	0.054
Internet Score		–	0.606	0.711	0.223	0.312
p-value			0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
Phone Score			–	0.488	0.187	0.207
p-value				0.000	0.008	0.003
Screen Time				–	0.393	0.341
p-value					0.000	0.000
Sleep Hours					–	0.275
p-value						0.001
Academic Score						–

This table shows Pearson correlation coefficients between variables related to internet/phone use and academic/lifestyle factors among students, along with their p-values to test the statistical significance of each correlation. The top part (values like $-0.155, 0.606$, etc.) shows the correlation coefficients (r -values). The bottom part (values like $0.004, 0.000$, etc.) shows the corresponding p-values, indicating if the correlation is statistically significant. A significant p-value is typically considered to be < 0.05 , meaning there's less than a 5% chance the result is due to random chance. Age have negatively correlated with Internet Score ($r = -0.155, p = 0.004$) Older students tend to have lower internet addiction. No significant correlation with Phone Score, Screen Time, Sleep Hours, or Academic Score.

Internet Score have strongly positively correlated with Phone Score ($r = 0.606, p = 0.000$) Students who use the internet more also use their phones more. Strong positive correlation with Screen Time ($r = 0.711, p = 0.000$) \rightarrow Higher internet use is linked to more screen time. Negatively correlated with Sleep Hours ($r = -0.223, p = 0.001$) \rightarrow More internet use is associated with less sleep. Negatively correlated with Academic Score ($r = -0.312, p =$

0.000) \rightarrow Higher internet use is linked to poorer academic performance.

Conclusion

Most participants in the study were aged 19 to 22 years, with the most common age being 20 years (25.6%). The age distribution resembled a near-normal curve, with a slight right skew due to older students. A significant majority (94.1%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science (BS) programs, while only 5.9% were in Pharm-D programs. Most students were from the 1st, 4th, and 6th semesters, indicating higher engagement among those in the early to mid-stages of their programs. Students were fairly evenly divided between internal (46.18%) and external hostels (53.82%).

Internet overuse was prevalent: nearly 94.1% of participants exceeded their intended online time to some extent, with 17.4% admitting to doing so constantly. Over 41% of students frequently neglected responsibilities, such as household chores, due to their internet usage. About 28.5% were secretive about their online habits, a behavioral indicator of possible addiction. A significant number of students reported using the internet to cope with disturbing thoughts, with over 22% doing this frequently.

Additionally, 28 to 35% of respondents expressed a sense of anticipation regarding their online activities and annoyance when interrupted, suggesting an emotional attachment to the internet. More than 53% experienced sleep loss attributable to internet use, and over 50% struggled to limit or reduce their online time. Procrastination and hiding their online usage were common behaviors, with many students showing signs of behavioral dependency on internet access.

Regarding interpersonal and academic impacts, around 44.8% reported that others frequently complained about their online habits. Furthermore, 55% stated that their academic performance was affected to some degree. Students who received more sleep tended to have better academic scores, while those with increased screen time or internet/phone usage showed poorer academic performance.

The study found that internet addiction was significantly predicted by phone addiction scores ($p = 0.000$) and age ($p = 0.036$), with older students tending to have slightly lower internet addiction scores. Phone addiction was significantly predicted only by internet addiction scores ($p = 0.000$). Factors such as degree program, semester, and hostel status were not significant predictors of either internet or phone addiction. The internet model explained 38% of the variance, and the phone model explained 36.9%, both considered moderate in behavioral research.

There was a strong correlation between internet and phone addiction ($r = 0.606$). Screen time showed strong positive correlations with both internet and phone addiction, while it negatively correlated with sleep and academic performance. Hours of sleep positively correlated with academic performance, highlighting the protective role of adequate rest.

The study reveals significant levels of smartphone and internet use among male boarding students, along with clear links to sleep disturbances, academic decline, and emotional reliance on digital platforms. Although most students do not meet the full criteria for addiction, many exhibit early or moderate signs of problematic behavior. These findings underscore the urgent need for awareness campaigns, time management education, and digital wellness interventions in hostel and university settings.

Further research should employ longitudinal designs and include female participants to enhance generalizability and explore gender-based differences in digital addiction.

References

- Mei, S...Hu, Y...Wu, X...Cao...R...Kong, Y... Zhang, L... & Li, L. (2023). Health risks of mobile phone addiction among college students in China. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 21(4), 2650-2665.
- Alotaibi, M. S., Fox, M., Coman, R., Ratan, Z. A., & Hosseinzadeh, H. (2022). Smartphone addiction prevalence and its association on academic performance, physical health, and mental well-being among university students in Umm Al-Qura University (UQU), Saudi Arabia. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(6), 3710.
- El-Gazar, H. E., Elgohari, H., Loutfy, A., Shawer, M., El-Monshed, A. H., Abou Zeid, M. A. G., & Zoromba, M. A. (2024). Does internet addiction affect the level of emotional intelligence among nursing students? A cross-sectional study. *BMC nursing*, 23(1), 555.
- Mohamed, Khalid O., et al.. Prevalence of internet addiction and its associated risk factors among medical students in Sudan: A cross-sectional study. *Cureus* 16.2 (2024).
- Whitaker, M. D., & Brown, S. (2020). Is mobile addiction a unique addiction: findings from an international sample of university students. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 18(5), 1360-1388.
- Jin Jeong, Y., Suh, B., & Gweon, G. (2020). Is smartphone addiction different from Internet addiction? comparison of addiction-risk factors among adolescents. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 39(5), 578-593.
- Niaz, U. (2008). Addiction with internet and mobile: An overview. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 5(2), 72-75.
- Renau, V., Gil, F., Oberst, U., & Carbonell, X. (2015). Internet and mobile phone addiction. In *Encyclopedia of mobile phone behavior* (pp. 807-817). IGI Global.

- Chiu, S. I., Hong, F. Y., & Chiu, S. L. (2013). An analysis on the correlation and gender difference between college students' Internet addiction and mobile phone addiction in Taiwan. *International scholarly research notices*, 2013(1), 360607.
- Chen, B., Liu, F., Ding, S., Ying, X., Wang, L., & Wen, Y. (2017). Gender differences in factors associated with smartphone addiction: a cross-sectional study among medical college students. *BMC psychiatry*, 17, 1-9.
- Liu, H., Zhou, Z., Zhu, E., Huang, L., & Zhang, M. (2022). Smartphone addiction and its associated factors among freshmen medical students in China: a cross-sectional study. *BMC psychiatry*, 22(1), 308.
- Nikolic, A., Bukurov, B., Kocic, I., Vukovic, M., Ladjovic, N., Vrhovac, M., & Sipetic, S. (2023). Smartphone addiction, sleep quality, depression, anxiety, and stress among medical students. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, 1252371.
- Tangmunkongvorakul, A., Musumari, P. M., Tsubohara, Y., Ayood, P., Srithanaviboonchai, K., Techasrivichien, T., & Kihara, M. (2020). Factors associated with smartphone addiction: A comparative study between Japanese and Thai high school students. *PLoS One*, 15(9), e0238459.

